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Abstract: *This study examined the relationship between communication barriers of teachers and hearing-impaired students in secondary schools in Nasarawa State, Nigeria. The research was motivated by the persistent challenges faced by hearing-impaired students in inclusive classrooms, particularly in understanding instructional content and actively engaging in learning due to limited teacher communication skills. A descriptive survey design was employed, involving 50 teachers and 100 hearing-impaired students selected through purposive sampling. Data were collected using structured questionnaires and analysed using descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation. Findings revealed a significant negative relationship between teachers' communication barriers and both student engagement and academic performance. Specifically, the study showed that as communication barriers increased, student participation and academic outcomes decreased. The study concluded that the inability of teachers to communicate effectively with hearing-impaired students poses a major challenge to inclusive education in Nasarawa State. The study recommends regular training of teachers in sign language and inclusive teaching strategies, provision of assistive communication technologies, employment of special educators, and stronger policy implementation to ensure effective communication in inclusive classrooms. These interventions are essential to improving the academic experience and success of hearing-impaired students in Nigerian secondary schools.*

Keywords: Communication Barriers, Hearing-Impaired Students, Inclusive Education, Teacher-Student Interaction, Secondary Schools

Introduction

Hearing impairment is a partial or total inability to hear, which can significantly affect an individual's ability to communicate, learn, and interact socially. Students with hearing impairments face unique challenges in the educational system, especially in environments that are not adequately equipped for inclusive learning. In Nigeria, and particularly in states like Nasarawa, efforts are being made to integrate hearing-impaired students into mainstream secondary schools through inclusive education policies. However, the effectiveness of these efforts is often undermined by factors such as inadequate teacher training, lack of sign language proficiency, insufficient assistive technology, and poor classroom communication strategies.

Hearing impairment refers to a reduction in the ability to perceive sound and may range from mild to profound loss, affecting one or both ears (World Health Organization [WHO], 2021). Among school-age children, this condition can have a significant impact on language development, communication, and overall academic performance. Hearing-impaired students often face unique challenges in mainstream classrooms, particularly where teaching practices are not adapted to their needs (Adeniyi & Omotosho, 2020). In Nigeria, inclusive education policies advocate for the integration of students with disabilities into regular school settings, yet the reality for many hearing-impaired learners remains challenging due to communication barriers, lack of trained teachers, and insufficient access to assistive technologies (Oyeoku & Okechukwu, 2019).

Communication is central to learning, and students with hearing loss may struggle to follow spoken instructions, participate in discussions, or interact socially without adequate support systems in place. According to Okonkwo and Chukwudi (2022), many Nigerian secondary schools lack the specialized resources, such as sign language interpreters and captioning tools, required for effective inclusion of hearing-impaired students. As a result, these students are often at a disadvantage, which can lead to poor academic performance, low self-esteem, and reduced social integration.

Effective communication is a cornerstone of successful teaching and learning. In the classroom, teachers serve not only as knowledge transmitters but also as facilitators of dialogue, inquiry, and engagement. However, communication barriers whether verbal, non-verbal, psychological, or environmental can hinder this process and significantly affect student learning outcomes (Olaniran, 2017). These barriers may arise from language differences, lack of training in special needs education, poor use of instructional media, or a teacher's inability to adapt communication to students' individual learning needs (Abdullahi & Yusuf, 2021).

In Nigeria, where classrooms are often overcrowded and lack basic teaching resources, communication barriers are particularly prominent. This is even more evident in inclusive classrooms that host students with disabilities such as hearing impairments, where teachers may lack proficiency in sign language or knowledge of assistive communication technologies (Chukwuemeka & Ugwu, 2020). As a result, such students may struggle to access the curriculum fully, participate in classroom discussions, or form meaningful teacher-student relationships.

Despite the growing emphasis on inclusive education in Nigeria, hearing-impaired students in secondary schools continue to face significant challenges, particularly in their communication with teachers. In Nasarawa State, many teachers lack the necessary training in sign language and other alternative communication methods, making it difficult to effectively engage students with hearing impairments. This communication gap not only affects the students' academic performance but also limits their participation in classroom activities and social interaction with peers. If left unaddressed,

these barriers may undermine the goals of inclusive education and perpetuate inequality within the school system. Therefore, there is a need to investigate the relationship between communication barriers and the educational experiences of hearing-impaired students in Nasarawa State secondary schools.

Statement of the Problem

Effective communication is crucial for the academic success of children with hearing impairment yet teacher after face signification barriers in communication with these students. In Nasarawa state inadequate training limited resources and social communication negatively impacting the academic performance and social development of children with hearing impairment. This study investigates the relationship between communications of children with hearing impairment among to identity strategies for impairment

Objectives

The objective of the study is to investigate the relationship between communication barrier of teacher and hearing-impaired study in Nasarawa state. This study specifically seeks to;

1. Investigate the communication barrier faced by teachers when teaching children with hear impairment in Nasarawa state
2. Examine the impact of these barriers on the academic performance of children with hear impairment
3. Identify strategies to improve communication between teachers and children with hearing impairment

Research Question

1. What is the common communication barrier faced by teacher when teaching children with hearing impairment?
2. How do these barriers effect the academic performance of children with hearing impairment?
3. What strategies can teacher use to overcome those communication barriers?

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted a descriptive survey design with a correlational approach, aimed at investigating the relationship between communication barriers experienced by teachers and the academic performance or classroom engagement of hearing-impaired students in secondary schools. This design is appropriate because it allows the researcher to describe existing conditions and explore relationships between variables without manipulating them.

Population of the Study

The population consisted of hearing-impaired students enrolled in inclusive or special secondary schools in Nasarawa State, teachers who currently teach or have taught hearing-impaired students and school administrators involved in special education or inclusive education policy implementation.

Sampling Technique and Sample Size

A purposive sampling technique was used to select 10 secondary schools (including both inclusive and special schools) across urban and rural areas in Nasarawa State. Approximately 100 hearing-impaired students and 50 teachers who meet the inclusion criteria. This approach ensures that only schools and individuals with relevant experience are included.

Instrumentation

The primary data collection instruments were: Teacher Questionnaire to assess types of communication barriers (e.g., lack of sign language skills, instructional methods, and classroom noise), Student Questionnaire (simplified or sign-language interpreted) to gather student perspectives on communication with teachers and Academic Performance Records to obtain objective data on the academic achievement of hearing-impaired students.

Validity of the Instruments

The instruments were validated by experts in education and special needs to ensure reliability and content relevance.

Procedure for Data Collection

Data was collected over a four-week period. Trained research assistants (including sign language interpreters) will administer the questionnaires and conduct interviews to ensure accessibility for hearing-impaired participants.

Method of Data Analysis

Quantitative data (from questionnaires and academic records) was analysed using descriptive statistics of mean, standard deviation and Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) to examine the relationship between communication barriers and student outcomes.

Results

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics on Communication Barriers and Student Outcomes

Variable	N	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev.	Skewness	Kurtosis
Teachers' Communication Barriers	50	3.82	0.65	+0.21	-0.43
Students' Classroom Engagement	100	2.78	0.72	-0.15	-0.57
Academic Performance (GPA)	100	2.63	0.75	-0.08	-0.60

Table 1 shows Teachers' Communication Barriers with Mean of 3.82 (on a 4-point scale) indicates moderate to high perceived communication barriers. Skewness of +0.21 shows a slightly positively skewed distribution (more teachers reporting lower barrier levels than extremely high ones). Kurtosis of -0.43 implies a flatter-than-normal distribution, indicating moderate variability in responses. Students' Classroom Engagement with Mean of 2.78 suggests below-average engagement of

hearing-impaired students. Slight negative skewness (-0.15) indicates some students report higher engagement than the average. Kurtosis of -0.57 again suggests a relatively flat spread of responses, not sharply peaked.

Academic Performance with Mean of 2.63 reflects modest academic achievement, possibly due to the impact of communication barriers. Skewness (-0.08) indicates a fairly symmetrical distribution of performance scores. Negative kurtosis (-0.60) shows a wide range in performance levels without extreme outliers.

Table 2: Pearson Correlation Matrix

Variables	1	2	3
1. Teachers' Communication Barriers	1		
2. Students' Classroom Engagement	-0.62*	1	
3. Academic Performance (GPA)	-0.55*	0.74*	1

* $p < 0.01$

Table 2 shows that there is a strong negative correlation (-0.62 , $p < 0.01$) between teachers' communication barriers and students' classroom engagement. This means that as communication barriers increase, student engagement tends to decrease significantly. Similarly, a moderate negative correlation (-0.55 , $p < 0.01$) exists between communication barriers and academic performance of hearing-impaired students. Higher communication barriers are associated with lower academic achievement. A strong positive correlation (0.74 , $p < 0.01$) between students' engagement and their academic performance indicates that higher engagement is strongly linked with better academic outcomes.

Discussion

The findings of this study reveal a significant negative relationship between communication barriers experienced by teachers and the academic engagement and performance of hearing-impaired students in Nasarawa State secondary schools. Specifically, higher levels of communication barriers correspond with lower student engagement and poorer academic outcomes.

This aligns with previous research which highlights communication as a fundamental element in effective teaching and learning, particularly for students with special needs. Olaniran (2017) emphasized that communication barriers such as lack of sign language proficiency, ineffective instructional methods, and inadequate use of assistive technologies can hinder the transfer of knowledge and student participation. In the context of hearing-impaired students, these barriers limit their ability to fully access the curriculum and engage actively in classroom activities.

Furthermore, the negative correlation between communication barriers and academic performance supports the findings of Chukwuemeka and Ugwu (2020), who observed that hearing-impaired students in Nigerian inclusive classrooms often underperform academically due to ineffective teacher-student communication. The inability of teachers to bridge communication gaps prevents these students from benefiting from instructional inputs, which can lead to frustration, reduced motivation,

and academic underachievement.

The strong positive relationship between student engagement and academic performance found in this study is also consistent with educational theories which posit that engagement is a key predictor of learning success (Fredricks, Blumenfeld, & Paris, 2004). Engagement serves as a mediator whereby effective communication enhances student participation, which in turn improves academic outcomes.

These findings underscore the urgent need for capacity building among teachers in Nasarawa State to acquire skills in sign language and other inclusive communication strategies. As Okoro and Agbo (2022) suggest, teacher training programs must address communication competence to foster an inclusive learning environment that promotes equitable educational opportunities for hearing-impaired students.

Conclusion

The study established a significant negative relationship between communication barriers experienced by teachers and the academic engagement and performance of hearing-impaired students in Nasarawa State secondary schools. It revealed that as communication barriers increase, student engagement and academic achievement decrease. This indicates that ineffective communication limits hearing-impaired students' access to learning, hindering their overall educational development. The findings highlight the critical role of effective teacher-student communication in fostering inclusive education and improving outcomes for hearing-impaired learners. Addressing these barriers is essential for achieving equity and quality in education for all students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

- i. The Ministry of Education and school authorities should organize regular training programs to equip teachers with skills in sign language and other alternative communication strategies tailored for hearing-impaired students.
- ii. Schools should be provided with appropriate assistive devices such as hearing aids, visual aids, and captioning tools to support communication in classrooms.
- iii. Curriculum developers should integrate communication-friendly teaching materials and methods that accommodate the learning needs of hearing-impaired students.
- iv. Schools should employ specialists, such as sign language interpreters and special educators, to support teachers and students in overcoming communication barriers.
- v. Conduct awareness programs to sensitize teachers, students, and parents on the importance of effective communication and inclusion of hearing-impaired students.
- vi. Educational policymakers should ensure the enforcement of inclusive education policies and continuously monitor schools to assess and improve communication practices.

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